

SOCIO –ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF FARM MACHINERY UTILIZATION
AMONG FARMERS IN AKURE SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO
STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the socio-economic factors affecting farm machinery utilization among farmers in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State. Data were collected from one hundred respondents randomly selected with the use of structured questionnaire. The analytical tools used were descriptive statistics and regression. Descriptive statistics was used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents while regression analysis was used to determine the socio-economic factors affecting farm machinery utilization in the study area. The study revealed that 79% were male, 72% married and 75% had formal education which will enhance their agricultural production. The regression result showed that age (x_1), family size, (X_2) and farm size (x_6) are significant. The coefficient of determination (R^2) which is 25.5% explained the variation in utilization of machines. It was recommended that government, financial institutions, NGOs, wealthy individuals should help in the improvement of credit facilities, road networks and rural electrification. Also, more awareness should be created among rural farmers on the need to change from traditional methods of farming to modern farming through farm mechanization. Finally, government should revive the already existing tractor hiring units in the Local Government Areas by purchasing new machineries, hire them out at affordable prices and ensure effective monitoring of thier operations.

KEYWORDS: Socio-economic, Farm machinery and Utilization

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INTRODUCTION

Food crisis in Africa particularly in Nigeria is becoming increasingly worrisome and an alarm has been raised in many quarters by government and non-governmental organisations, agricultural practitioners, researchers, scholars and consumers. For instance, the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO, 2009) of the United Nations has alerted developing countries about possible steep rises in food prices in 2011 and beyond. According to the FAO, with the pressure on world prices of most commodities not abating, the international community must remain vigilant against further supply of shocks. According to the organisation, world cereal production is likely to contract by 2%, global cereal stocks may decline sharply, international prices of wheat has increased by 12%, more serious food crisis anticipated in 2015. In Africa, some countries such as Burkina Faso, Mauritania, Guinea, Gabon etc have demonstrated against soaring food prices. In Nigeria, 63 billion naira was spent on food importation in one year (CBN, 2010). Market information from Ondo State revealed that the price of rice per better life bowl has increased from ₦200-₦300, ₦220 - ₦280 and gari ₦100 - ₦150 food production is required.

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In response to this alarm and to forestall the looming food crisis, many policies have been formulated, agricultural programmes designed, research institutes established and farmers have been making efforts to adopt and utilize output-increasing technology generated by the research institutes through the persuasion of the extension agents to boost food production.

Unfortunately, the emphasis of the extension arm of the ministry of agriculture has always been on the adoption of biological innovations i.e improved plant varieties to the neglect of mechanization services thereby resulting to small farm sizes, low level of output and farm income forgetting the fact that an increase in farmers cultivated land area through mechanization would permit profitable use of other innovations.

Tools, implements and powered machinery are essential and major inputs to agriculture. The term mechanization is usually used as the application of those inputs (Clark, 2002). The level, appropriate choice and subsequent proper use of mechanized inputs into agriculture has a direct and significant effects on achievable level of land productivity, the profitability of farming, the sustainability, the environmental and the quality of the life of people engaged in agriculture.

Agricultural development involves three approaches namely; biochemical, socio economic and engineering known as the trio of technology (Mrema and Odigboh, 1993). The biochemical approaches includes the development of improved animal and plant nutrients (fertilizer and feed) and plant and animal protection (Veterinary drugs, pesticides and herbicides). The socio-economic approaches include financial packages as management programmes (Economics, Business Management, Accounting, Sociology, Extension Service, and Agricultural Marketing and Price Structure).

The engineering approaches deals with the provision of agricultural machineries and equipment (be they humans, animal, or mechanically powered) for production and post-harvest handling and storage systems and farm structures, erosion control measures, water resources development as well as irrigation and drainage structures, meteorological systems, and technologies for optimal utilization of the above and their proper economic use and management. Onwualu and Pawa (2004) reported that agricultural mechanization as a system of engineering requires not only advance in machine development and application but also close cooperation of many sections. Conditions must be ascertained to favour investment in mechanization technologies and their sustainable use. Timeless of tillage and planting, weeding and harvest are critical factors where affordable labour is insufficient to permit operation. It is against this background that this study intends to identify and estimate factors influencing farm mechanisation services in Ondo State.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State. The Local Government occupies the land area of about 250square kilometres with a population of about 353,211 habitants according to 2006 population census (NPC, 2006). It is bounded in the North by Akure North Local Government. Towns in the Local Government are Akure and Oda while the villages include Aule, Adofure, Illekun, Apomu, Itaoniyang, Gaga, Emiloro. etc.

Multi-stage randomly technique was used to select ten (10) communities and ten (10) respondents from each of the communities making 100 as the sample size. Data for this study were collected through the use of structured questionnaire supplemented with oral interview. Data were collected on the socio economic variables such as age, family size, marital status, level of education etc. and non-demographic variables such as type of farm machinery used by the respondents, source of the machinery and problems encountered in their usage.

Data collected were analysed by the use of descriptive statistics such as tables, frequency distribution, and percentage. Regression analysis was used to determine the socio-economic factors affecting farm machinery utilization.

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The model is specified below:

$$Y = f (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, X_{10}, E) \dots\dots\dots(1).$$

Y = Yield (kg)

X₁ = Age of the respondents (Years)

X₂ = Family size

X₃ = Gender

X₄ = No of years spent in school

X₅ = Cost of hiring tractor and farm implements (Naira)

X₆ = Farm size (Hectares)

E = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study showed that 82% of the respondents were below 60 years. This may imply that they are strong enough to engage in farm production. Majority (79%) of the respondents were male. This may imply that men were more involved in farming activities than women in the study area. The result further showed that 88% of the respondents were married which may indicate that taking farming as a profession can generate enough income to sustain their families.

The study also revealed that 85% of the respondents had formal education. This may help the respondents in the use of mechanization on the farm. On machinery application, 72% of the respondents depended on hiring service while 26% used lease arrangement with only (2%) having personal farm machines. This may be a confirmation of the fact that they are small scale farmers without enough financial capacity to purchase tractor and other farm machineries.

Majority (82%) of the respondents were aware of the tractor hiring service in their Local Government Area. This may imply that the tractor hiring units of the local government area are functional but 68% complained of high cost which limited their access to those farm machineries.

The study however showed that there were a lot of problems limiting the utilization of machinery among farmers in the study area. They include capital (26%), untimely response (10%), operational technique (32%), and land exposure to erosion (31%). This implies that for efficiency and efficient machinery utilization these problems must be addressed.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF FARM MACHINERY UTILIZATION

The explanatory variables: age (x₁), family size (x₂), gender (x₃), level of education (x₄), cost of hiring machine (x₅) and farm size (x₆) were regressed against the yield (kg) of farmers in the area. The coefficient of determination (R²) was 25.2% implying that 25% of the variation in farmers yield was explained by the explanatory variables. The regression equation is shown below:

$$Y = 0.123 + 0.387* x_1 + 0.126*x_2 - 0.002x_3 - 0.009x_4 - 0.010x_5 + 0.021*x_6 \dots\dots\dots (2).$$

(0.214) (0.028) (0.044) (0.006) (0.006) (0.027) (0.027)

R² = 0.252

F2 = 47.683

The regression results (equation 2) indicated that age, family size and farm size were positive and significant at 5% implying that these explanatory variables were important economic determinants of the yield of farmers using farm machines in the study area. Their positive signs indicated that an increase in their values will increase the output of farm machine users while others: gender (x₃), no of years spent in school (x₄) and cost of hiring machines (x₅) were negatively signed i.e. an increase in their value would reduce the farmers yield.

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CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

The results of this study indicated that majority of the respondents were aware of the use of farm machines as a means of boosting their farm yield but an insignificant proportion claimed they owned their own machines implying a complete dependence on other sources governmental or non – governmental. Also, the fact that farm size was a significant determinant of farmers output implied that increasing the cultivated land area through the use of farm machines would boost farmers output level.

However, the major problems limiting the use of farm mechanization in the study area is the high hiring cost born out of the fact that the State farm service centres have neglected farm mechanization services leaving farmers at the mercy of private tractor owners. Equally worrisome is the inadequate finance to purchase improved production technologies. Farm service centres should therefore be invigorated to reduce hiring cost. The present agricultural credit scheme embarked upon by the State government is a step towards the right direction and therefore should be vigorously and sincerely implemented. Farmers should be organised into cooperatives to facilitate their access to credit and farm mechanisation services.

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Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristic of Respondents.

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
Below 20	2	2.0
20-39	23	23.3
40-59	57	57.0
60 & above	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0
Gender		
Male	79	79.0
Female	21	21.0
Total	100	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	12	12.0
Married	72	72.0
Divorced	10	10.0
Widowed	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0
Level of Education		
No formal Education	15	15.0
Primary School	28	28.0
Secondary School	26	26.0
Adult Education	5	5.0
Tertiary Education	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Table 2: Method of Machinery Acquisition used by the Respondents

Method of acquisition	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Personal	2	2.0
Hired	72	72.0
Lease	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Table 3: Awareness on Tractor Hiring Services

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	82	82.0
No	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010

Table 4: Cost of Tractor Hiring Incurred by the Respondents

Cost of hiring	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high	68	68.0
High	20	20.0
Low	12	12.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

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Table 5: Problems Encountered in using Machines on the Farm

Problems	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Inadequate capital	26	26.0
Untimely response	10	10.0
Operation techniques	32	32.0
Land exposure to erosion	31	31.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

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